
IMPACT OF GREEN MARKETING ON CONSUMER BEHAVIOR AND DECISION MAKING**Dr. Rakesh Garg**

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ABSTRACT

Green marketing is going to be proactive topic with it steps into the world of the consumers where consumers are not only aware for the multiple brands and their perceived quality but also they have started to pay more attention to the environment and thereby becoming more eco friendly. Therefore the companies are also exploring the various ways for communicating with the customers so that customers can be retained as loyal for long by adopting green management.

The purpose of this research is to investigate the impact of green marketing on consumer purchasing patterns and decision making in India. This paper attempts to analyze the correlations between environmental belief factors (eco-labeling, green branding and packaging, environmental advertisements, green pricing, embedding an eco-image, environmental concerns and beliefs) and the environmental behaviour of consumers. The significant findings show that intensity of green packaging and green branding, importance of green products and premium green pricing have a significantly positive impact on consumer behaviour leading to green purchases. Correlations were found between eco-labeling, green branding and green pricing and the environmental behaviour of consumers.

Keywords: *Green Marketing, Consumer Awareness, Consumer Buying Decisions, etc.*

INTRODUCTION

The concept of green marketing is the business practice that considers consumers concerns with regards to preservation and conservation of the natural environment (Cordington, 1993). It refers to the process of selling products and/or services based on their environmental benefits. Such a product or service may be environmentally friendly in it or produced and/or packaged in an environmentally friendly way. The term Green Marketing got attention and importance in late 1980's and early 1990's when specific products were identified as being harmful to earth's atmosphere. Defining green marketing is not a simple task where several meanings intersect and contradict each other. "Green Marketing" involves developing and promoting products and services that satisfy customer's needs and wants for quality, performance, affordable pricing and convenience with minimum environmental harm not necessarily eliminating it. Companies that excel in green marketing will benefit from better relations with customers, regulators, suppliers and other firms in their industry. According to Pattie (2001), the green marketing has evolved over a period of time. **First phase** was termed as "Ecological" green marketing, **Second phase** was "Environmental" green marketing and **Third phase** was "Sustainable" green marketing.

GREEN PRODUCTS AND ITS CHARACTERISTICS

The products those are manufactured through green technology and that caused no environmental hazards are called green products. Promotion of green technology and green products is necessary for conservation of natural resources and sustainable development. We can define green products by following measures:

- Products those are originally grown,
- Products those are recyclable, reusable and biodegradable,
- Products with natural ingredients,
- Products containing recycled contents, non-toxic chemical,
- Products contents under approved chemical,
- Products that do not harm or pollute the environment,
- Products that will not be tested on animals,
- Products that have eco-friendly packaging i.e. reusable, refillable containers etc.

GREEN BUYING BEHAVIOUR

It is essential to analyse green buying behaviour of green consumers in order to identify the factors that are driving the consumer purchase patterns, including the intention of purchase and actual purchase behaviour of green products. Grob (1995) defines behaviour in environmental context as actions that have a direct effect on the ecosystem. There are multiple green practices that are gaining momentum. Some of them include recycling,

saving paper and electricity, avoiding the use of aerosols, encouraging the use of biodegradable products, use of organic food and so on (Gilg et al., 2005). Consumer demand in terms of green movement is gradually sloping upwards (Han et al., 2010). The reason for this shift towards green purchases could be a result of consumers' realization of the impact their behaviour has on the environment.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To analyze the correlations between environmental belief factors (eco-labelling, green branding and packaging, environmental advertisements, green pricing, embedding an eco-image, environmental concerns and beliefs) and the environmental behaviour of consumers.
2. To understand the marketing mix of green marketing.
3. To know the golden rules and marketing strategies of green marketing.
4. To suggest some measures for consumers to increase the green practices.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Pride and Ferrell (1993) Green marketing, also alternatively known as environmental marketing and sustainable marketing, refers to an organization's efforts at designing, promoting, pricing and distributing products that will not harm the environment. A research agenda is finally suggested to determine consumers' awareness of environmental justice, and their willingness to bear the costs associated with it.

Oyewole, P. (2001). In his paper presents a conceptual link among green marketing, environmental justice, and industrial ecology. It argues for greater awareness of environmental justice in the practice for green marketing. A research agenda is finally suggested to determine consumer's awareness of environmental justice, and their willingness.

Brahma, M. & Dande, R. (2008). The Economic Times, Mumbai, had an article which stated that, Green Ventures India is a subsidiary of New York based asset management firm Green Ventures International. The latter recently announced a \$300 million India focused fund aimed at renewable energy products and supporting trading in carbon credits.

Sanjay K. Jain & Gurmeet Kaur (2004). In their study environmentalism have fast emerged as a worldwide phenomenon. Business firms too have risen to the occasion and have started responding to environmental challenges by practicing green marketing strategies.

Kilbourne, W.E. (2011) discussed the failure of green marketing to move beyond the limitations of the prevailing paradigm. The author identified areas that must be examined for their effect in the marketing/environment relationship, namely economic, political and technological dimensions of the cultural frame of reference.

Prothero, A. (2012) introduced several papers discussed in the July 1998 issue of 'Journal of Marketing Management' focusing on green marketing. This included a citation of the need to review existing literature on green marketing, an empirical study of United States and Australian marketing managers, a description of what a green alliance look like in practice in Great Britain, ecotourism and definitions of green marketing.

Prothero, A. & Fitchett, J.A. (2013) argued that greater ecological enlightenment can be secured through capitalism by using the characteristics of commodity culture to further progress environmental goals. Marketing not only has the potential to contribute to the establishment of more sustainable forms of society but, as a principle agent in the operation and proliferation of commodity discourse, also has a considerable responsibility to do so.

Oyewole, P. (2014) in his paper presented a conceptual link among green marketing, environmental justice, and industrial ecology. It argues for greater awareness of environmental justice in the practice for green marketing. A research agenda is finally suggested to determine consumer's awareness of environmental justice, and their willingness to bear the costs associated with it.

Karna, J., Hansen, E. & Juslin, H. (2015) interpreted that proactive marketers are the most genuine group in implementing environmental marketing voluntarily and seeking competitive advantage through environmental friendliness. The results also give evidence that green values, environmental marketing strategies, structures and functions are logically connected to each other as hypothesized according to the model of environmental marketing used to guide this study.

Rayapura (2016) in support cites a Nielsen global study which showed that 55% of global online consumers across sixty countries surveyed expressed willingness to pay more for products and services from companies that area dedicated to positive social and environmental impact.

GREEN BRANDING

One of the most significant elements of green branding strategies is green positioning which can further be classified into functional or emotional. Elements that are classified as emotional are considered more important compared to functional elements of branding and green positioning of products (Meffert and Kirchgeorg, 1993). According to Sarkar (2012), when green positioning is used in terms of a corporate strategy, it can be based on different emotional brand benefits such as selflessness associated with emotion of well-being, benefits including auto-expression that are a result of using socially recognizable green brands and nature related benefits (Sarkar, 2012, p. 47).

GREEN ADVERTISEMENTS

Green advertisements first incepted in late 1960s as a result of concerns brought up by consumer activism, public and scientific communities and others about firms using anti-environmental practices (Easterling et al., 1996). Over the years, green advertising decreased because of false claims via advertisements, exaggeration in the advertisement content and it was found that consumers' were perplexed about the terminologies used (Polonsky et al., 1997). Yin and Ma (2009) state that green advertising caught momentum again in 2000s, with developments in international legislations, global support, renewed interest among consumers and so on, therefore starting the sustainable age (Belz and Peattie, 2009). Green advertisements refer to adverts including sustainability of the environment, eco-friendly content, substance targeting needs and desires of green consumers and other stakeholders (Zinkhan and Carlson, 1995).

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

Questionnaires provide the researcher an opportunity to collect data from a large sample size with a low possibility of the responses' distortion (Saunders et al., 2009). With an intention to collect large amount of data with negligible distortion of responses, this research has adopted the Questionnaire instrument for this quantitative study. Since the research was associated with buying behaviour of consumers with regard to green marketing, the participants included regular supermarket visitors from different gender, age groups, education qualification and place of residence. The gender was coded as Female=1 and Male=2. The age group was further divided into tertiles (18-23=1, 23-38=2, and 39-62=3). The highest education level was divided into three and coded as Intermediate=1, Graduate=2 and Masters=3. The place of residence was coded as Urban=1 and Rural=2. To facilitate the research, 100 surveys were sent out to participants from Haryana, India, of which 80 complete responses were received. Correlation and Regression analysis are both used to analyse the relationships between variables, however, correlation analysis shows the degree of association while regression analysis shows the relationship between dependent and independent variables.

Hypothesis 1: There is a positive relationship between green branding and packaging and the environmental behaviour of consumers.

Hypothesis 2: There is a positive relationship between green advertising and the environmental behaviour of consumers.

Hypothesis 3: There is a positive relationship between green pricing and the environmental behaviour of consumers.

Hypothesis 4: There is a positive relationship between environmental concerns and beliefs and the environmental behaviour of consumers.

DATA ANALYSIS

The internal consistency is used to measure the correlation of responses between the different questions of the questionnaire. Cronbach's alpha (>0.7) is considered as a reliable technique to measure the internal consistency of questionnaires with multiple items (Gliem and Gliem, 2003).

To analyse the descriptive statistics, test of normality is done using the Shapiro-Wilk test and distributions of histograms. Depending on the normality or the deviation from it, statistical tests on different groups are carried out. The P value shows the significance level and for $P < 0.05$, the null hypothesis is rejected and for $P > 0.05$, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table : 1

Variable	Frequency	Valid %
Categorical Variables Gender		
Female	45	56.3
Male	35	43.8
Age		
18-23	26	32.5
23-38	27	33.8
39-62	27	33.8
Highest Education Level Attained		
Intermediate	20	25
Graduates	38	47.5
Masters	22	27.5
Place of Residence		
Urban	69	86.3
Rural	11	13.8

Table: 2: Correlation between Factors of Environmental Beliefs and Environmental Behaviour

Variables	R	Sig.
Effectiveness of eco-labeling and green products identification	.250*	.027
Intensity of green packaging and branding for ecological customers	.318**	.004
Environmental advertisement and green consumption patterns	.120	.291
Importance of green products and premium green pricing	.365**	.001
Embedding an eco-image in marketing of green products	.065	.572
Consumers' perceptions on environmental concerns and beliefs	.026	.819

In the case of the correlation between effectiveness of eco-labelling and green product identification and environmental behaviour, it can be observed that there is a very weak positive correlation between the variables ($R=.250$), however, it is statistically significant ($P=.027$). Similarly, correlation between importance of green products and premium green pricing and the environmental behaviour is positive but weak and statistically significant ($R=.365$, $P=.001$). In the case of green branding, correlation is significant at 0.01. So, considering the correlation between intensity of green packaging and branding and the environmental behaviour, a statistically significant and positive weak correlation can be found ($R=.318$, $P=.004$). There is no correlation or statistical significance between embedding an eco-image in marketing of green products ($R=.065$, $P=.572$), green advertisements ($R=.120$, $P=.291$) or consumers' perceptions on environmental concerns and beliefs ($R=0.26$, $P=.819$) and environmental behaviour.

RESEARCHERS HAVE IDENTIFIED MANY REASONS FOR WHICH A MARKETER SHOULD GO FOR ADOPTION OF GREEN MARKETING

1. Marketers must see green marketing as an opportunity to achieve its objectives because all types of consumers both individual and industrial are becoming more concerned and aware about the natural environment and have modified their purchasing behavior accordingly. It is believed that the marketing of green goods will have a competitive advantage over the other goods simultaneously meeting their business objectives.
2. Many organizations have started to realize that they have a moral obligation to be more socially responsible. This is in keeping with the philosophy of CSR which has been successfully adopted by many business houses to improve their corporate image. Firms in this situation can take two approaches:
 - Use the fact that they are environmentally responsible as a marketing tool.
 - Become responsible without prompting this fact.
3. Governmental bodies are forcing firms to become more responsible. In most cases the government forces the firm to adopt policy which protects the interests of the consumers. It does so in following ways:
 - By banning production of harmful goods or by products
 - By banning consumption of harmful goods; or

- Evaluating the system by which a consumer can evaluate sub standard products easily.
- 4. Competitors' environmental activities may be a pressure for the other firms to change their environmental marketing activities. In order to get pace with competitors claim to being environmentally friendly, firms must change over to green marketing. It is believed that green marketing will infiltrate the entire industry. As society has become more concerned with the natural environment, some firms have begun to modify their behavior in an attempt to address society new concerns.

GOLDEN RULES OF GREEN MARKETING

1. **Know you're Customer:** Make sure that the consumer is aware of and concerned about the issues that your product attempts to address, (Whirlpool learned the hard way that consumers wouldn't pay a premium for a CFC-free refrigerator because consumers dint know what CFCs were.).
2. **Educating your customers:** Isn't just a matter of letting people know you're doing whatever you're doing to protect the environment, but also a matter of letting them know why it matters. Otherwise, for a significant portion of your target market, it's a case of "So what?" and your green marketing campaign goes nowhere.
3. **Being Genuine & Transparent:** Means that a) you are actually doing what you claim to be doing in your green marketing campaign and b) the rest of your business policies are consistent with whatever you are doing that's environmentally friendly. Both these conditions have to be met for your business to establish the kind of environmental credentials that will allow a green marketing campaign to succeed.
4. **Reassure the Buyer:** Consumers must be made to believe that the product performs the job it's supposed to do-they won't forego product quality in the name of the environment.
5. **Consider Your Pricing:** If you're charging a premium for your product-and many environmentally preferable products cost more due to economies of scale and use of higher-quality ingredients-make sure those consumers can afford the premium and feel it's worth it.
6. **Giving your customers an opportunity to participate:** Means personalizing the benefits of your environmentally friendly actions, normally through letting the customer take part in positive environmental action.
7. **Thus leading brands should recognize that consumer expectations have changed:** It is not enough for a company to green its products; consumers expect the products that they purchase pocket friendly and also to help reduce the environmental impact in their own lives too.

GREEN MARKETING MIX

Understanding the target consumer will help marketers to know whether "greenness" is an appropriate selling attribute and how it should be incorporated into the marketing mix. Every company has its own favorite set of marketing mix. Some have 4 P's and some have 7 P's of marketing mix. The 4 P's of green marketing are that of a conventional marketing but the challenge before marketers is to use 4 P's in an innovative manner if they wanted to adopt the policy of green marketing.

A. Green Product: The products have to be developed depending on the needs of the customers who prefer environment friendly products. Products can be made from recycled materials or from used goods. Efficient products not only save water, energy and money, but also reduce harmful effects on the environment. Green chemistry forms the growing focus of product development. The marketer's role in product management includes providing product designers with market-driven trends and customer requests for green product attributes such as energy saving, organic, green chemicals, local sourcing, etc., For example, Nike is the first among the shoe companies to market itself as green.

B. Green Price: Green pricing takes into consideration the people, planet and profit in a way that takes care of the health of employees and communities and ensures efficient productivity. Value can be added to it by changing its appearance, functionality and through customization etc. Wall Mart unveiled its first recyclable cloth shopping bag.

C. Green Place: Green place is about managing logistics to cut down on transportation emissions, thereby in effect aiming at reducing the carbon footprint. For example, instead of marketing an imported mango juice in India it can be licensed for local production. This avoids shipping of the product from far away, thus reducing shipping cost and more importantly, the consequent carbon emission by the ships and other modes of transport.

D. Green Promotion: Green promotion involves configuring the tools of promotion, such as advertising, marketing materials, signage, white papers, web sites, videos and presentations by keeping people, planet and profits.

GREEN MARKETING PRACTICES IN INDIA

1. **Tata Steel:** Tata Steel commits to install technology to minimize the adverse impact of its processes on the environment by conserving the natural resources & energy by reducing the consumption and wastage & recycling of materials. Developed and rehabilitate waste dumps through a forestation and landscaping. Maintaining and operating the facilities with applicable Environmental laws, statutes and other regulations.
2. **Indian Railways:** Recently IRCTC has allowed its customers to carry PNR no. of their E-Tickets on their laptop and mobiles. Customers do not need to carry the printed version of their tickets.
3. **Wipro's Green Machines:** Wipro InfoTech was India's first company to launch environment friendly computer peripherals. For the Indian market, Wipro has launched a new range of desktops and laptops called Wipro Green ware. These products are ROHS (Restriction of Hazardous Substances) compliant thus reducing e-waste in the environment.
4. **State Bank of India:** SBI is providing many services like; paper less banking, no deposit slip, no withdrawal form, no checks, no money transactions form all these transaction are done through SBI shopping & ATM cards. State Bank of India turns to wind energy to reduce emissions. The wind project is the first step in the State Bank of India's green banking program dedicated to the reduction of its carbon footprint and promotion of energy efficient processes, especially among the bank's clients.
5. **Forest and Environment Ministry of India:** Has ordered to some retail outlets like Big Bazaar, More, Central, D-Mart that they should provide polythene carry bags to those customers only that are ready to pay a price for it.

GREEN MARKETING IN INDIA: INITIATIVES TAKEN BY THE GOVERNMENT AS WELL AS BY VARIOUS ORGANIZATIONS

Considering the importance of the environment for human beings, the Indian Government as well as various organizations is taking 'green initiatives' for the sake of environmental protection and sustainability.

INITIATIVES TAKEN BY ORGANIZATIONS

Various initiatives have been taken by various organizations for adopting environment friendly practices/ green practices, some of them are as follows:-

- HCL launched HCL ME 40, its range of eco-friendly notebooks. HCL claims that it is an eco-friendly notebook free from polyvinyl chloride (PVC). Further, this product was given a five-star rating by the Bureau of Energy Efficiency. They also meet REACH (REACH is the European Community Regulation on chemicals and their safe use) standards and are 100% recyclable and toxin free (Rediff.com: Here are some of India's leading 'Green' Companies, 2011).
- In 2007, Voltas (Tata Group) launched the 'Green' range of air-conditioners, following which it was made mandatory by the government to have energy star ratings for electronic home appliances. Energy Star is a well known international standard for energy efficient consumer products that originated in the United States (Rediff.com: Here are some of India's leading 'Green' Companies, 2011).
- Wipro also launched eco-friendly desktops which were introduced under the Wipro Green Ware initiative, with an aim to cut down e-waste. The systems launched are toxin free and operate under a total recycling policy. Wipro has 17 e-waste collection centers in India where products are collected and recycled, and 12 Wipro campuses in the country have been certified as green buildings (Rediff.com: Here are some of India's Leading 'Green' Companies, 2011).
- ACC recently launched its eco-friendly brand, 'Concrete+'. This brand uses fly ash (a hazardous industrial waste) to help conserve natural resources as dumping of fly ash is a major environmental problem, thus making it an eco- friendly product. The new product has been designed exclusively to ensure high durability (Rediff.com: Here are some of India's Leading 'Green' Companies, 2011).
- MRF launched eco-friendly tubeless tyres MRF ZSLK, which are made from unique silica-based rubber compounds and promises to offer fuel efficiency for vehicle owners (Rediff.com: Here are some of India's Leading 'Green' Companies, 2011).

- Pidilite has launched environment friendly synthetic resin adhesive named Fevicol AC Duct King Eco Fresh. It is claimed to be the first eco-friendly adhesive of India and boasts of being an all-in-one adhesive. The company officials say that this water-based adhesive spreads easily and smoothly at room temperature, without emitting any harmful fumes and is suitable for residential as well as industrial projects (Rediff.com: Here are some of India's Leading 'Green' Companies, 2011).
- Haier India took the green initiative by launching its 'Eco-Life' series electronic products aimed at designing smart and environment friendly products that should fulfill environmental norms along with meeting customers' needs. The range of electronic products the company is offering through this series includes refrigerators, all ranges of automatic washing machines, split and window air conditioners, a wide range of water heaters and LED & LCD TVs (Rediff.com: Here are some of India's Leading 'Green' Companies, 2011).
- P&G India introduced compact detergents in India for Ariel and Tide using fewer raw materials and packaging material, while ensuring superior consumer value. P&G India also redesigned the pump package of their beauty product Olay, which reduces plastic consumption and is 25% lighter than the earlier packaging. Re-designing the pump package has saved over 400 tonnes of packaging a year (the weight of a Boeing 747) (P&G, 2013).
- SBI is using eco and power friendly equipment which consumes less electricity in its new ATMs, which has helped SBI to save power costs and earned it carbon credits. SBI opened its first green banking branch at Jotsoma Science College in Kohima under the green banking initiative of State Bank of India (The Times of India, 2012).

INITIATIVES TAKEN BY THE GOVERNMENT

The following are the initiatives taken by the Government of India:-

- The Reserve Bank of India has requested the Non Banking Financial Corporations (NBFCs) to take proactive steps and initiatives to increase the use of electronic payment systems, and to gradually phase-out cheques and eliminate post-dated cheques in their routine business transactions as a part of "Green Initiative" (Department of Financial Services, Government of India : Green Initiative Master Circular, 2012).
- The Finance Minister announced ` 600 crore for green initiatives in the Union Budget, 2011 mainly for the protection and regeneration of forests and for environmental management.
- The Government has set up various standards for environment protection such as energy efficiency standards for appliances (refrigerators, air conditioners, tube lights, transformers, and other electrical appliances), energy conservation building code (ECBC), and fuel efficiency/emission norms for vehicles (Ministry of Environment and Forest, Government of India, 2010).
- The Ministry of Corporate Affairs (MCA), Government of India has taken a 'Green Initiative in the Corporate Governance' vide its Circular Nos. 17/2011 dated 21.04.2011 and 18/2011 dated 29.04.2011 which enables the entity to deliver all important documents to shareholders in the electronic form (i.e. to their e-mail address) that have been registered with the depository participants, including the notice of extra ordinary general meeting, annual general meeting, director's reports, audited financial statements, and so forth (Octane Research, 2013).
- In the Government's report of annual Indian economic survey 2011-2012, sustainable development and climate change was introduced for the first time, where lower-carbon sustainable growth was proposed as a central element of India's 12th five-year-plan (Patankar, 2012).
- According to an estimate, India spent approximately US\$45 billion on green IT and sustainability initiatives in the year 2012, and the figure may reach US\$70 billion by 2015, fueled by the Government's push for greater adoption (Yap, 2012).

CONCLUSION

Today companies from all fields have come up with different forms of green marketing, though the government and many private companies have been making an effort to bring about a green mindset among the people and promote green products, a lot still need to be done to make green products truly viable and workable especially in India. Based on the results, it was gathered that effectiveness of eco-labelling had a positive effect on the consumers' environmental behaviour. It was also observed that environmental advertising had a negative effect on environmental behaviour; similar result was found in terms of environmental concerns and beliefs of consumers and its relationship to the environmental behaviour. This shows that consumers are concerned about

the environment, but they are reluctant to purchase green products. In terms of correlations also, no significant correlation was found between the environmental concerns of consumers, environmental advertising and eco-image and the environmental behaviour of consumers. Further research, with a bigger sample size might be able to shed more significant insights with regard to these findings. The green marketers in India should carry out heavy promotional campaigns, because a majority of the Indian consumers are not sure about the quality of the green products.

With the threat of global warming looming large, it is extremely important that green marketing becomes the norm rather than an exception or just a fad. Recycling of paper, metals, plastics, etc., in a safe and environmentally harmless manner should become much more systematized and universal. It has to become the general norm to use energy-efficient lamps and other electrical goods. Marketers also have the responsibility to make the consumers understand the need for and benefits of green products as compared to non-green ones. In green marketing, consumers are willing to pay more to maintain a cleaner and greener environment. Finally, consumers, industrial buyers and suppliers need to pressurize effects on minimize the negative effects on the environment-friendly. Green marketing assumes even more importance and relevance in developing countries like India. Live a green life and let the greenery of nature live forever.

SUGGESTIONS

- ✚ Environment friendly behaviour is far and difficult to attain. Hence environmental awareness and attitudes should be created in the minds of consumers during their childhood days itself.
- ✚ It requires rigorous efforts at school level to create an attitude of environment sustainability.
- ✚ Eco clubs play an important role in creating environmental awareness amongst the future generation. So eco clubs should be there in all schools and colleges.
- ✚ Expand the consumer awareness of green products by creating effective green marketing campaigns or environmental related activities. The companies should try to more focus on the green features of the product in their marketing activities.
- ✚ Price is the attribute that consumers reflect on when making a green purchasing decision. Consumers are less likely to purchase green products if they are more expensive. So price should be reduced for the eco-friendly products.
- ✚ Companies should create ads that are more focused on green, eco-friendly image that will influence their customers purchasing decision.

FUTURE RESEARCH

The future research could take a new approach to this study by using mixed approach using survey to collect the quantitative data complemented with qualitative data by means of in-depth interviews, to study the drivers of green consumer behaviour like green branding and premium green pricing, over a period of time. Studies could be undertaken to identify why green advertising has a negative impact on environmental behaviour of consumers even though green branding has found to have a positive impact on the same.

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